

Correlations Between Religiosity, Locus of Control and 16 Personality Factors in Hindu and Christian College Going Students.

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Abstract: The religion and religiosity are important aspect of human life. Every human society participate religion in the one form or another. Personality is supposed to be related with religiosity as later has influences on many behaviours. However, the study of personality and religiosity has been neglected. Locus of control is also such personality variable which determine the belief of control over events. This locus of control also should be related with religiosity and personality. This investigation is done on 120 college going students, out of which 60 were Hindu and 60 were Christian consisting of 30 males and 30 females. The scores obtained on religiosity, personality and locus of control measure run for Pearson coefficient of correlation. Religiosity and locus of control are positively associated. Factors A, C, G, H, and Q3 are found related with religiosity. Factor I and locus of control is positively related.

Keywords: Religiosity, Personality factors, locus of control.

I Introduction

Religion and Religiosity:

A human being along with *Homo sapiens* is *Homo psychologicus* as well as *Homo religious*, this implies that human being is practicing religion since very long time rather it is supposed to be indispensable part of the life of humans. Every human group or society has been practicing the religion in one form or another (Smith C., 2017). Many scholars have been attempted to define religion albeit no one have offered inclusive and comprehensive definition. The word religion is etymologically originated from Latin word *religare* which means to tie, to restrain or to bind. Nongbri asserts that, religion is word applied for the discussion about god and other superhuman beings and ways to interact with them. According to Christian Smith religion is aggregate of rituals or practices ordained by particular culture involving belief system about existence and nature of personal or impersonal superhuman powers and involving such practices in order to gain access or communicate or aligning oneself with such superhuman powers. Durkheim defined religion as "A unified system of beliefs and practices related to sacred things, which unite into one single moral community." In general, it can be said that, religion is kind of belief system, practice of constellations of rituals, involving supernaturally powerful god and aimed at resulting good life and avoiding catastrophe or any bad fortune. Being religious can be explained by evolutionary, cognitive, anthropological, social and many such theories. There are many primary and secondary gains (Smith C.) of being religious. The being religious is know as religiosity. A person adhered to any particular religious belief system and obey the cultural practices and rituals or follow the religion in any form is called religiosity. More the person stick to the religious practices and

norms greater will be the religiosity. For being religious it is suffice to adhere to the ritualistic practices without or with knowledge or having effects on behaviour and feeling of those practices and beliefs (Paloutzian, 2017). According to Peterman et al., (2002), social form of religious practices involving group or organization is also referred as religiosity.

Personality:

Personality is highly studied construct in psychology, rather to understand a person holistically personality render the power to student of psychology. Personality is originated from the Latin word *persona* which means the mask wore by artists in the Greek drama to play the particular character. Personality is the persons behaviour in totality whether overt and covert and the field of psychology is called personality psychology (Boeree, 2006; Cloninger, 2009; Feist, Feist, & Roberts, 2018). The personality is the characteristics patterns of behaviour, emotions, and cognitions in any particular environment that enable person to deal with and adjust to that situation for better or worse.

Locus of Control

Jullian Rotter proposed the prediction formula of the behaviour as $B = f(E \times V)$ and state that behaviour is depended on the reinforce expectancy and value of reinforcement (Feist, Feist, & Roberts, 2018; Ryckman, 2008; Ellis, Abrams, & Abrams, 2009). Locus of control is the belief developed by a person about the control of life events or situation by external forces outside of a person or an internal forces like response to situational stimulus or behaviour or locus of control is kind of perception about the external or internal control over reinforcer or reward (Rotter, 1966).

Religiosity and Personality

There is growing interest in studying relationship between personality and religiosity, however this relationship or religiosity construct was neglected by psychologists. Maximum studies on religiosity and personality have done by using Big Five personality model encompassing traits namely extraversion, neuroticism, conscientiousness, agreeableness and openness to experience. Before that Eysenck's PEN model also has used involving traits like psychoticism, extraversion, and neuroticism. Very few if any studies found on 16 PF and religiosity. The positive relationship between neuroticism and religiosity was found in adults, adolescents and children (Ekehammar & Sidanius, 1982, Francis, Lankshear, and Pearson, 1989, Francis and Pearson, 1988). More the person religious more the introverted, (Francis 1989). A meta-analytic study revealed that religiosity was associated with low psychoticism (Lodi-Smith & Roberts, 2007). In meta-analysis done by Soroglou in 2010, it was found that agreeableness and conscientiousness related positively with religiosity and openness to experience was not related to religiosity. In one study, the neuroticism, extraversion and openness to experience were found negatively related and agreeableness and conscientiousness were not related (Sontakke, 2017). The HEXICO variables like honesty- humility, emotionality, agreeableness, and conscientiousness were positively related with religiosity (Lee, Ogunfowara, and Ashton 2005, Aghababaei, Wasserman, & Nannini, 2014). The religiosity is negatively related with M and Q1 factors from 16 personality factors. The factor G is positively correlated with religiosity, (Meredith 1968). In a study by Bourke, Francis, and Robbins on secondary school students found that, significant negative relationship is found between attitude towards Christianity and factor E and F, and on the opposite positive correlation between attitudes towards Christianity and factor G, I and, Q3 respectively.

Religiosity and Locus of Control

The relationship between locus of control and religiosity is equivocal. Both internal and external locus of control is found to be related with religiosity, (Friedberg & Friedberg, 1985, Slatinsky, Farren, Bartlett, Fiaud, & Haasl, 2022). Some studies reported intrinsic religious orientation is positively associated with internal locus of control. There are some studies which have reported no relation between locus of control and religiosity (Friedberg & Friedberg, 1985; Lowis, Edwards, & Burton, 2009; Wong-McDonald & Gorsuch, 2004).

Personality and Locus of Control

There are some studies which directly examine the relationship between personality traits and locus of control. There are some studies which are interested in studying the combined influence of personality traits

and locus of control. The researchers wish to differentiate the persons with internal and external locus of control in terms of personality traits of Big five. In one such study researcher found that person with external locus of control and internal locus of control differ significantly on all Big five traits. Persons with internal locus of control were more open to experience and neurotic. On the other hand, externals were higher on remaining three traits namely conscientiousness, extraversion and agreeableness, (Bhalerao, T., 2022). In another study, there is no significant difference between conscientiousness and internals scored significantly higher on openness than externals. On the contrary externals scored significantly higher on extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism, (Shinde, R., 2022). The internal locus of control is found to be positively related with extraversion, openness, agreeableness, and conscientiousness, or in other words external locus of control is negatively related with four above mentioned traits and positively related with neuroticism, (Zitny, P. & Halama, P., 2011, Kandi & Zeinali, 2017). In one study researcher reported that, the internal locus of control is negatively correlated with conscientiousness, whereas all other big five factors are not related. External locus of control is positively correlated with openness to experience, and it exhibited no correlations between extraversion, agreeableness, neuroticism, and conscientiousness. No study found on 16 personality factors and locus of control.

Objective

In present study investigator wish to study correlations between religiosity, locus of control and 16 personality factors in Hindu and Christian college going students.

Hypotheses

In this study researcher has hypothesised that:

1. The Religiosity and locus of control will show significant relationship in Hindu and Christian college going students.
2. The Religiosity and 16 personality factors will exhibit significant relationship in Hindu and Christian college going students.
3. The locus of control and 16 personality factors are significantly related with each other, in Hindu and Christian college going students.

Methods

Sample

To test the above stated hypotheses researcher selected 60 Hindu and 60 Christian students, out of which in both religion group 30 were male and 30 females by conventional and snowball sampling methods. The age range for Hindu females is 19-23 years with mean 19.97, and for males is 18-25, with mean 21.53 years. Christian females age range is 18- 26 with mean age 21.66 years and Christian males age range is also 18-26 with mean age 21.23 years

Tools

Religiosity Scale: The religiosity scale constructed by Dr. L. I. Bhushan and Dr. Jayprakash has been used. It consists of 36 items with five-point response scale from completely agree to completely disagree. Its split half reliability is 0.72 and content validity is good.

16 PF Questionnaire: 16 PF questionnaire is used to measure personality traits. This scale is formed by Raymond Cattell. As name suggests it assess 16 personality factors called A (Warmth), B (Abstract Thinking), C (Emotional stability), E (Dominance), F (Surgency), G (Rule Consciousness), H (Socially Bold), I (Tender Minded), L(Vigilance), M (Imaginative), N (Shrewdness), O (Apprehension), Q1 (Radicalism), Q2 (Self – Reliance), Q3 (Controlled), Q4 (Tense). Both split half and parallel form reliability coefficients range from 0.6 to 0.9 for all factors and construct validity coefficient range from 0.35 to 0.92 for all factors.

Locus of Control: Hindi adaptation of Rotter’s locus of controlled scale Dr. Anand Kumar and Dr. S. N. Srivastava is used to assess locus of control. It consists of 29 items pairs out of which participant has to choose one item which s/he thinks relevant for her/him. The split half reliability coefficient is 0.88 and test- retest reliability coefficient is 0.85. The test has good discriminant validity.

Statistical Analysis: Pearson product moment coefficient of correlation is computed between religiosity, locus of control and 16 personality factors.

Results

Results obtained are shown in table no. I the Pearson product moment coefficients between religiosity, locus of control and 16 personality factors are shown. The significant correlations are flagged.

Table No. I. Pearson product moment coefficient of correlations between religiosity, locus of control and 16 personality factors

	Religiosity	Locus of Control
Religiosity	1	
Locus of Control	.354**	1
Factor A	.234*	.129
Factor B	.135	.035
Factor C	.214*	.100
Factor E	-.150	-.041
	.101	.655

Factor F	.062	-.129
	.504	.160
Factor G	.208*	.031
	.023	.736
Factor H	-.281**	-.172
	.002	.060
Factor I	.162	.292**
	.077	.001
Factor L	-.083	-.036
	.365	.700
Factor M	-.039	-.073
	.671	.427
Factor N	.009	.039
	.920	.669
Factor O	-.098	-.096
	.285	.299
Factor Q1	-.071	.030
	.440	.742
Factor Q2	-.078	-.001
	.398	.993
Factor Q3	.195*	.138
	.033	.132
Factor Q4	-.097	-.176
	.294	.055

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level.
 * . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level.

From table no. I, it is revealed that, religiosity and locus of control is significantly positively related. Factor A is positively related with religiosity, and does not show relationship with locus of control. Factor B is not related with either religiosity or locus of control. Factor C is positively related with religiosity and not related with locus of control. Factor E shows negative non-significant correlation with both religiosity and locus control. Factor F shows non-significant positive relation with religiosity and non- significant negative relations with locus of control. Factor G shows significant positive relation with religiosity and non-significant positive relation with locus of control. Factor H is significantly negatively correlated with religiosity however, locus of control is negatively non-significantly related. Religiosity shows non- significant positive relation with factor I where as locus of control shows positive and significant relation with factor I. Factors L, M, O, Q2, and Q4 shows negative but non-significant relationship with both religiosity and locus of control. Factors N and Q3 both shows positive relationship with religiosity as well as locus of control, however factor Q3 is significantly related with religiosity and non- significantly with locus of control

respectively, where as factor N shows no significant relationship with both religiosity and locus of control.

Discussion

In the present study investigator hypothesised the significant relationship between religiosity and locus of control. Results are in favour of this as coefficient of correlation ($r= 0.354$, $df= 118$) is significant. There are numerous studies which supports this finding. External locus of control is related with high religiosity and Internal locus of control is associated with internal religious orientation (Wiley, 2006; Sawai, 2018, Rastegar, Heidari, & Razmi, 2013, Iles-Caven, Gregory, Ellis, Golding, & Nowicki, 2020). Thus, people with high religiosity appears to possess external locus of control, possible explanation is persons having external locus of control have a faith in some external agency like god who has a control over world, they also believe in fate or luck as causal agent (Slatinsky, Farren, Bartlett, Fiaud, & Haasl, 2022). Notwithstanding there are many having high religiosity, have a tendency to explain events in terms of external causality or internal control (Friedberg & Friedberg, 1985, Slatinsky, Farren, Bartlett, Fiaud, & Haasl, 2022).

Religiosity and personality also exhibit inconsistent associations. In present investigation high religiosity is found to be associated with factor A, C, G, H, and Q3 from 16 personality factors. Remaining factors are not correlated. Factor A is cold- warmth, that is, higher score on A represent high warmth trait. Factor H represents social boldness which is one of the contributors in big extraversion trait. This social boldness also found positively related with high religiosity. Intrinsic general religiosity and open mature religiosity is positively related with extraversion, (Saroglou, 2002). Some studies found negative relationship between extraversion and religiosity, (Francis, 1989, Jayshree Sontakke, 2017). Some studies reported no relationship between extraversion and religiosity, (Ehsan & Pournaghash, 2012). Factor C that is emotional stability is found positively related in present study, similar results are also produced by (Ehsan & Pournaghash, 2012, Saroglou, 2002, Fiasse & Saroglou, 2003, Soroglou, 2010, Lee, Ogunfowara, and Ashton 2005). One contradictory finding about relationship between emotional stability and religiosity is also reported, (Sontakke, 2017). The high religious person is found to be highly conscientious, as factor G is positively related with religiosity (Meredith, 1968, Saroglou, 2010, Fiasse & Saroglou, 2003, Parveen, 2011). Factor Q3 (perfectionism) is positively related with high religiosity this is also in concordance with above cited studies producing positive relationship between conscientiousness and religiosity.

Bourke, Francis, and Robbins in 2007 found similar results in study done on high school students.

Only factor I that is tender minded is related with locus of control and all other factors are not related. Since tender minded are sensitive, they are open to experience. The positive relations are found between openness to experience and external locus of control, (Bhalerao, T., 2022). There are studies which produced dissimilar results that is internal locus of control is associated with

openness, (Zitny, P. & Halama, P., 2011, Kandi & Zeinali, 2017, Shinde, 2022).

Conclusion

There are ambivalent findings in this investigation in a way religiosity, personality, and locus of control related with each other. However, there are many similar studies like the present study. Since only two religions are selected for this study, more religions and a greater number of participants can be included. Contribution of religiosity in personality can also be studied. There are very few studies with 16 pf and hence more studies are sought on religiosity and 16 pf.

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